

AN ANALYSIS OF KISAN CREDIT CARD: A TOOL FOR AGRICULTURAL FINANCE IN INDIA

Dr. Jeet Singh
Assistant Professor, Moradabad Institute of Technology, Moradabad

Dr. Preeti Yadav
Lecturer, Institute of Rural Management, Jaipur

Article No:206

ISSN 0974 – 9497

Year: February 2011

Volume 5, Issue 1/4

Abstract: Rural development means nothing but the transformation of the subsistence agricultural production to a market oriented agricultural economy. Availability and access to financial resources is one of the key elements to this transition. Financial resource is a very important, if not the most important, factor in economic development. Shortage of finance is one of the major problems facing small farmers. Farmers need financial resource to buy improved agricultural inputs and farm implements so that they can increase their output and income level and break the cycle of poverty. Farmer's investment in these technologies cannot be real without having in place organizations and systems that are capable of adequately providing rural financial services to farmers. So, the effort to develop agriculture could suffer in the absence of a strong financial base that aims at expanding access to credit for small farmers. The delivery mechanism for agricultural credit in India is fundamentally flawed. This has been acknowledged in the media; numerous academic studies commissioned by the government and non governmental agencies, and is borne out by the dismal economic condition of the average Indian farmer.

The paper looks into the agricultural credit in terms of Kisan Credit Card. Consequent upon the announcement in the budget speech for the year 1998-99, NABARD, in consultation with major banks, formulated a model scheme for issue of Kisan Credit Card. The scheme aimed at adequate and timely financial support in a flexible and cost effective manner from the banking system to the farmers for their cultivation needs including purchase of inputs. The scheme was circulated to banks by RBI/NABARD.

Kisan card within short span of time has established itself as a fairly popular credit product among the farming community. It is expected that this would help the farmers in easy and timely access to much desired institutional credit. The study brought out the fact that Kisan card has been appreciated and accepted both by the bankers as well as farmers. Despite all this, Kisan card scheme is not free of problems. Based on the discussion held in the field with farmers and bankers, the paper brought out certain issues relating to policy as well as operational aspects of Kisan card which may require attention of the agencies concerned.

The paper highlights the agricultural credit scenario in India and focuses on the role of formal financial institutions in delivery of agricultural credit. The study notes that both formal and informal sources of credit are important in the India context. However, the significance of formal credit institutions in terms of credit delivery for the agricultural sector has increased over time. The main formal financial institutions involved in the delivery of agricultural credit are commercial banks, co-operative banks and Regional Rural Banks.

This paper attempts to analyse the issues in agricultural credit in India. The analysis reveals that the credit delivery to the agriculture sector continues to be insufficient. It appears that the banking system is still hesitant on various grounds to provide credit to small and marginal farmers. The paper presents the result

of the survey on agricultural credit conducted in village Asmoli, the biggest village in Moradabad district in Sambhal constituency in Uttar Pradesh.

Key Words: Agriculture finance, kisan credit card, NABARD, rural finance

Introduction: Agriculture Finance

Agricultural production in India depends upon millions of small farmers. It is the intensity of their effort and the efficiency of their technique that will help in raising yields per acre. Because of inadequate financial resources and absence of timely credit facilities at reasonable rates, many of the farmers, even though otherwise willing, are unable to go in for improved seeds and manures or to introduce better methods or techniques. It is, therefore, of the utmost importance that the financial requirements of the farmers are adequately met. Finance in agriculture is as important as development of technologies. Technical inputs can be purchased and used by farmer only if he has money (funds). But his own money is always inadequate and he needs outside finance or credit.

Professional money lenders were the only source of credit to agriculture till 1935. They use to charge unduly high rates of interest and follow serious practices while giving loans and recovering them. As a result, farmers were heavily burdened with debts and many of them perpetuated debts. There were widespread discontents among farmers against these practices and there were instances of riots also.

With the passing of Reserve Bank of India Act 1934, District Central Co-op. Banks Act and Land Development Banks Act, agricultural credit received impetus and there were improvements in agricultural credit. A powerful

alternative agency came into being. Large-scale credit became available with reasonable rates of interest at easy terms, both in terms of granting loans and recovery of them. Both the co-operative banks advance credit mostly to agriculture. First bank advances short-term and medium term loans while the second bank advances long-term loans. The Reserve Bank of India as the Central bank of the country took lead in making credit available to agriculture through these banks by laying down suitable policies.

Although the co-operative banks started financing agriculture with their establishments in 1930's real impetus was received only after Independence when suitable legislation were passed and policies were formulated. There after, bank credit to agriculture made phenomenal progress by opening branches in rural areas and attracting deposits.

Till 14 major commercial banks were nationalized in 1969, co-operative banks were the main institutional agencies providing finance to agriculture. After nationalization, it was made mandatory for these banks to provide finance to agriculture as a priority sector. These banks undertook special programs of branch expansion and created a network of banking services through out the country and started financing agriculture on large scale. Thus agriculture credit acquired multi-agency dimension. Development and adoption of new technologies and availability of finance go hand in hand. In bringing "Green Revolution", "White Revolution" and

now “Yellow Revolution” finance has played a crucial role. Now the agriculture credit, through multi agency approach has come to stay.

The procedures and amount of loans for various purposes have been standardized. Among the various purposes “Crop loans” (Short-term loan) has the major share. In addition, farmers get loans for purchase of electric motor with pump, tractor and other machinery, digging wells or boring wells, installation of pipe lines, drip irrigation, planting fruit orchards, purchase of dairy animals and feeds/fodder for them, poultry, sheep/goat keeping and for many other allied enterprises. Rural development means nothing but the transformation of the subsistence agricultural production to a market oriented agricultural economy. Availability and access to financial resources is one of the key elements to this transition. Financial resource is a very important, if not the most important, factor in economic development.

Shortage of finance is one of the major problems facing small farmers. Farmers need financial resource to buy improved agricultural inputs and farm implements so that they can increase their output and income level and break the cycle of poverty. Farmer’s investment in these technologies cannot be real without having in place organizations and systems that are capable of adequately providing rural financial services to farmers. So, the effort to develop agriculture could suffer in the absence of a strong financial base that aims at expanding access to credit for small farmers.

Agricultural loans are available for a multitude of farming purposes. Farmers may apply for loans to buy inputs for the cultivation of food grain crops as well as for horticulture, aquaculture, animal husbandry, floriculture and sericulture businesses. There are also special loans to finance the purchase of agricultural machinery such as tractors, harvesters and trucks. Construction of biogas plants and irrigation systems as well as the purchase of agricultural land may also be financed through special types of agricultural finance.

Review of the Literature

The genesis of institutional involvement in the sphere of agricultural credit could be traced back to the enactment of the Cooperative Societies Act in 1904. The establishment of the RBI in 1935 reinforced the process of institutional development for agricultural credit. The RBI is perhaps the first central bank in the world to have taken interest in the matters related to agriculture and agricultural credit, and it continues to do so (Reddy, 2001). The increased outreach and access to agricultural credit in the post bank-nationalisation period coupled with augmented demand due to the Green Revolution of 1960s and enhanced focus on directed priority sector lending⁵ could not correct the weaknesses in the rural financial delivery system over the years which adversely affected the viability and sustainability of these institutions (Mohan, 2006). though the credit disbursement in rural areas has increased manifold the same has not affected any increment in the agricultural GDP. This may be due to a continuous decline in the total factor productivity in Indian Agriculture (Rao & Gulati 2005) caused

by the absence of a suitable technological breakthrough in Indian agriculture in the post-green revolution era.

Research Methodology

Research in common parlance refers to a search for knowledge. One can also define research as a scientific and systematic search for pertinent information on a specific topic. The present study has been undertaken to examine the issues and challenges to be addressed by means of agriculture finance.

The present paper aims to achieve the following objectives:

- To analyse the issues in agricultural credit in India
- To look into the agricultural credit in terms of Kisan Credit Card.

Area of Study

The paper is not confined to any particular area; on the other hand it is applicable to whole India. However,

Types of Agriculture Credit Needs

Credit needs of the farmers can be examined from two different angles-

<u>ON THE BASIS OF TIME</u>	<u>ON THE BASIS OF PURPOSE</u>
Short Term	Productive
Medium Term	Consumption
Long Term	Unproductive

(A) On the Basis Of Time

- **Short time** (for periods up to 15 months): Short term loans are required for the purchase of seeds fertilizers, pesticides, feeds, marketing of agriculture produce, payment of wages of

opinion of officers/managers of various banks in Moradabad district of Uttar Pradesh has been taken about the growth, roadblocks and benefits of agriculture credit. Their views have been incorporated in this paper. The paper also takes the references of various articles written by various experts on agriculture credit and especially kisan credit card.

The paper presents an analysis of the survey conducted in village Asmoli of Moradabad district regarding the use of kisan credit card issued by Prathma Bank (A RRB promoted by Syndicate Bank, Government of India and Government of UP). A sample size of 50 farmers was taken.

We have used qualitative research techniques as focus group discussion with respect to implementation of rural credit. Our focus group discussion was based on agriculture credit. The discussions were based on key issues with emphasis on kisan credit card.

hired labour, litigation and variety of consumption and unproductive purposes. The period of such loans is less than 15 months. Main agencies granting loans are moneylenders & cooperative societies. These

are expected to be repaid after the harvest.

- **Medium term** (from 15 months up to 5 years): Medium term loans are required for purchase of cattle, small agri implements, repair & construction of wells etc. The periods of such loan extends from 15 months to 5 years. The loan is provided by moneylenders, relative of farmers, co-operative societies and commercial banks etc.
- **Long term** (above 5 Years): Long term loans are required for effecting permanent improvements of land, digging of tube wells, purchase of larger implements, machinery like tractor and repayments of old debts. The period of such loan extends beyond 5 years.

(B) On the Basis Of Purpose

- **Productive:** Farmers need loans for the purchase of seeds fertilizers, pesticides, feeds, marketing of agriculture produce, livestock, repair of wells, payments of wages etc.
- **Consumption:** Farmers require loans for consumption as well. Between the moment of marketing of agricultural produce and harvesting of next crop there is long interval of time and most of farmers don't have much income to sustain in this period. Also times of flood drought, damages to crop etc.
- **Unproductive:** Purposes such as litigation, performance of marriages, birth or death,

religious functions, festivals. Institutional agencies do not grant credit for unproductive and consumption purposes and farmers have to seek assistance from money lenders and mahajans.

Issues Involved In Agriculture Finance

There are three major issues before the rural financial institutions which need attention for making the agriculture sector make a significant contribution to the economic growth of the country:

- (1) The quantum of flow of institutional credit to agriculture has to be increased;
- (2) The access to formal credit for the rural poor and disadvantaged and agriculturally less developed regions has to be improved; and
- (3) The economic viability of rural banking system has to be ensured over time.

Constraints of Agricultural Financial Services

The constraints in agricultural financial services providing agriculture finance are:

- 1) **Cheap, Adequate and Timely Supply:** The credit required by farmers has got to be cheap i.e. low rate of interest. Today's profit oriented institutions are not likely to supply cheap credit. Adequate and timely credit has got to be available. Most of institutions require collateral for adequate credit. The Banks procedure for granting loans is tedious too.

- 2) **Small Farmers and Landless Labourers:** Those who have large land can mortgage their land and get credit for specialized institutions. But lot of farmers own small piece of land in India, therefore to grant loans without any collateral is difficult one.
- 3) **High Information and Transaction Costs:** This linked to poor infrastructure (roads, telecommunications) and lack of client information. (no personal identification or functioning asset registries)the loans advanced are small, interest earned is smaller but to grant loan certain machinery is functioning which results in high transaction cost.
- 4) **Weak Institutional Capacity of Rural-Finance Providers:** This is related to the limited availability of educated and well-trained people in smaller rural communities. The staffs of rural banks are not equipped with education, training, and other skills to support functioning of those banks. Most of times the staff is from neighborhood area.
- 5) **Uncertainty Shrouding Credit Requirements:** In industrial sector, due to forecasting of demand, prices profits, one can prepare the plan of borrowing and repayment. In case of agriculture everything is uncertain.
- 6) **Seasonality of Many Agricultural Activities:** Agricultural activities in India are seasonal; carried out during certain period which Results in variable demand for savings and credit, uneven cash flow and lags

between loan disbursal and repayments.

Sources of Agricultural Finance

Sources of agricultural finance can be divided into two categories:

(A) Non Institutional Sources

- **Traders and Commission Agents:** Traders and commission agents advance loans to agriculturists for productive purposes against their crop without completing legal formalities. It often becomes obligatory for farmers to buy inputs and sell output through them. They charge a very heavy rate of interest on the loan and a commission on all the sales and purchases, making it exploitative in nature. It an important source of finance in case of cash crops like cotton, tobacco and groundnut.
- **Landlords:** Mostly small farmers and tenants depend on landlords for meeting their production and day to day financial requirements.
- **Money Lenders:** At the time of independence the most important source of agricultural credit was the moneylenders. Moneylenders accounted for as much as 71.6 % of rural credit. The prominent position of moneylender is due to non availability of other source. Therefore moneylender exploits the farmer in number of ways as we have seen in bollywood films. Therefore govt. has undertaken various steps to regulate activities of moneylenders. For the purpose, various legislations were enacted.

(B) Institutional Sources

The evolution of institutional credit to agriculture could be broadly classified into four distinct phases - 1904-1969 (predominance of co-operatives and setting up of RBI), 1969-1975 [Nationalisation of commercial banks and setting up of Regional Rural Banks (RRBs)], 1975-1990 (setting up of NABARD) and from 1991 onwards (financial sector reforms).

- 1) **Government:** These are both short term as well as long-term loans. These loans are popularly known as “Taccavi loans” which are generally advanced in times of natural calamities. The rate of interest is low. But it is not a major source of agricultural finance.
- 2) **Cooperative Credit Societies:** The history of cooperative movement in India dates back to 1904 when first Cooperative Credit Societies Act was passed by the Government. The scope of the Act was restricted to establishment of primary credit societies and non-credit societies were left out of its purview. The shortcomings of the Act were rectified through passing another Act called Cooperative Societies Act 1912. The Act gave provision for registration of all types of Cooperative Societies. This made the emergence of rural cooperatives both in the credit and noncredit areas, though with uneven spatial growth. In subsequent years a number of Committees were appointed and recommendations implemented

to improve the functioning of the cooperatives. Soon after the independence, the Government of India following the recommendations of All India Rural Credit Survey Committee (1951) felt that cooperatives were the only alternative to promote agricultural credit and development of rural areas. Accordingly, cooperatives received substantial help in the provision of credit from Reserve Bank of India as a part of loan policy and large scale assistance from Central and State Governments for their development and strengthening. Many schemes involving subsidies and concessions for the weaker sections were routed through cooperatives. As a result cooperative institutions registered a remarkable growth in the post-independence India.

- 3) **Commercial Banks:** Previously commercial banks were confined only to urban areas serving mainly to trade, commerce and industry. Their role in rural credit was meager i.e., 0.9 per cent in 1951- 52 and 0.7 per cent in 1961-61. The insignificant participation of commercial banks in rural lending was explained by the risky nature of agriculture due to its heavy dependence on monsoon, unorganized nature and subsistence approach. A major change took place in the form of nationalisation of commercial banks in 1969 and commercial banks were made to play an active role in agricultural credit.

At present, they are the largest source of institutional credit to agriculture.

4) **Regional Rural Banks:**

Regional Rural Banks (RRBs) were set up in those regions where availability of institutional credit was found to be inadequate but potential for agricultural development was very high. However, the main thrust of the RRBs is to provide loans to small and marginal farmers, landless labourers and village artisans. These loans are advanced for productive purposes. At present 196 RRBs are functioning in the country lending around Rs 9,000 crore to rural people, particularly to weaker sections.

5) **Micro-financing:**

Micro-financing through Self Help Groups (SHG) has assumed prominence in recent years. SHG is group of rural poor who volunteer to organize themselves into a group for eradication of poverty of the members. They agree to save regularly and convert their savings into a common fund known as the Group corpus. The members of the group agree to use this common fund and such other funds that they may receive as a group through a common management. Generally, a self-help group consists of 10 to 20 persons. However, in difficult areas like deserts, hills and areas with scattered and sparse population and in case of minor irrigation and disabled persons, this number may range from 5-

20. As soon as the SHG is formed and a couple of group meetings are held, an SHG can open a Savings Bank account with the nearest Commercial or Regional Rural Bank or a Cooperative Bank. This is essential to keep the thrift and other earnings of the SHG safely and also to improve the transparency levels of SHGs transactions. Opening of SB account, in fact, is the beginning of a relationship between the bank and the SHG. The Reserve Bank of India has issued instructions to all banks permitting them to open SB accounts in the name of registered or unregistered SHGs.

National Bank For Agriculture And Rural Development (NABARD)

The present study will not be completed without mentioning the functions of NABARD. Set up in 1982, National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD) is the apex institution accredited with all matters concerning policy, planning and operations in the field of credit for agriculture and other economic activities in rural areas in India. NABARD serves as an apex refinancing agency for the institutions providing investment and production credit in rural areas.

The National Bank of Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD) was set up in 1982 by the Government of India with the following mandate:

- 1) To serve as a refinancing institution for all kinds of

- production and investment credit to agriculture, small scale industries, cottage and village industries, handicrafts and rural crafts and rural artisans and other allied economic activities with a view to promoting integrated rural development;
- 2) To provide short-term, medium-term and long-term credits to state Co-operative Banks (SCBs), RRBs, LDBs and other financial institutions approved by RBI;
 - 3) To give long-term loans (upto 20 years) to the State Governments to enable them to subscribe to the share capital of co-operative credit societies;
 - 4) To give long-term loans to any institution approved by the Central Government or contribute to the share capital or invest in securities of any institution concerned with the agriculture and rural development;
 - 5) Responsibility of co-ordinating the activities of Central and State Governments, the Planning Commission and other All-India and State Level Institutions entrusted with the development of Small Scale Industries, Village and Cottage Industries, Rural Crafts, Industries, in the tiny and decentralised sectors etc.;
 - 6) Responsibility to inspect RRBs and co-operative banks, other than primary co-operative banks; and
 - 7) To maintain a research and development fund to promote research in agriculture and rural development to formulate and design projects and Programme to suit the requirements of

different areas and to cover special activities.

NABARD to Launch 3,000 Farmers' Clubs In Up

National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD) will launch 3,000 Farmers' Clubs across Uttar Pradesh in the current fiscal. These are expected to act as catalyst to boost agriculture production in the state. More than 7,500 clubs were already working in the state. These bodies work as extended arms of NABARD. According to statistics, the villages having intervention of Farmers' Clubs are zero Non Performing Assets (NPA) villages for the Bank. Meanwhile, NABARD is working towards appointing the club members as Business Facilitators and Business Correspondents to achieve the target of 100 per cent financial inclusion. The programme has proved to be a strong instrument of development in rural areas. This scheme has been sponsored by Prathma Bank, India's first Regional Rural Bank (RRB). NABARD provides grant to these clubs for sustainability and 'meet with expert' programmes. During 2008-09, it released a grant of Rs 68 lakhs towards various promotional programmes organised through the clubs.

Challenges Facing Agriculture Finance

- | |
|---|
| (a) Farmers financially distressed |
| (b) Suppliers of finance not financially sustainable |
| (c) Development impact not achieved - cannot isolate the positive effect of finance to the emerging successes |

(d) Farming not profitable?

Banks Hesitant To Provide Finance To Farmers

Banks either government or private, both are hesitant to provide loans to farmers. In spite of various attempts made by government and RBI, banks are not liberal in granting loans to farmers. According to RBI instructions, banks have to give 18 percent of Adjusted Net Bank Credit to agriculture sector. But from the last three years, 50 percent banks have failed to achieve this target. In providing loans to farmers government banks stand in line with private banks. This is evident from the answer provided by Finance Minister Shri Pranab Mukherjee to Rajya Sabha. By the end of financial year 2008-09, 13 government banks were there who have

failed to provide the farmers' share of finance. The worst position was of Corporation Bank, IDBI Bank and State Bank of Travencore who have just given 11 percent of Adjusted Net Bank Credit to farmers. Similarly, Bank of Baroda, Bank of Maharashtra, State Bank of Patiala, United Bank of India and Oriental Bank of Commerce were failed to provide 18 percent of credit to farmers. Earlier to this in the financial year 2006-07 and 2007-08 also nearly 50 percent of banks were failed to achieve the target of providing credit to farmers. Similarly, 14 private sector banks had shown carelessness in granting loans to farmers in the last financial year. The worst performance were of Bank of Rajasthan, City Union Bank and Karnataka Bank who failed to give even 9 percent of the loans to the farmers.

Amount of Loans Given By Public Sector Banks

The table below shows the number of accounts opened and the amount of loans given by public sector banks.

	No. of Accounts ('000)				Amount (Rs. In Crore)			
	June 1969	Mar'06	Mar'07	Mar'08	June 1969	Mar'06	Mar'07	Mar'08
Direct Finance	160	22079	23746	27908	40	112126	144372	176135
Indirect Finance	10	1719	1367	441	122	43093	58242	72550
Total	170	23798	25113	28349	162	155219	202614	248685

The above table shows that the amount of loans given by public sector banks was Rs. 248685 crores in the year ended March 2008 as compared to Rs. 202614 crore and Rs. 155219 crore in the year ended March 2007 and March 2006 respectively, which is not a remarkable increase in these three years.

Kisan Credit Card - An Innovative Product

In spite of various measures to rejuvenate farm credit, the flow of credit remained quantitatively and qualitatively poor. The institutional sources of credit meet only 51 per cent of the credit requirements of farm sector. The non-

institutional sources were mainly reached by farmers due to lack of collaterals, frequent needs, undue delays, complicated procedures and malpractices adopted by institutional lending agencies. With a view to inquire into the reasons for the problems of the farm credit and suggest measure for improving the delivering system, RBI set up a one man Committee of Shri R. V. Gupta to in December 1997. The Committee submitted its report in April 1998. It was against this background that RBI directed all Public Sector Banks (PSBs), RRBs and cooperative banks to introduce "Kisan Credit Card Scheme (KCCS)" on the lines of the model scheme formulated by NABARD and in due course of time the KCCS was adopted by all the directed agencies.

Kisan Credit Cards were started by the Government of India, RBI (Reserve Bank of India), and NABARD (National Bank for Agricultural and Rural Development) in 1998-99 to help farmers access timely and adequate credit. The Kisan Credit Card allows farmers to have cash credit facilities without going through the credit screening processes repeatedly. Repayment can be rescheduled if there is a bad crop season, and extensions are offered for up to 4 years. The card is valid for 3 years and subject to annual renewals. Banks in India that lend for agricultural purposes usually offer the KCC. Withdrawals are made using slips, cards, and a passbook.

It is intended that both term as well as short term/working capital credit facilities will be provided through single Kisan Credit Card. The passbook provided to KCC holders are to be

divided into three separate portions for maintaining the records of:-

- Short term credit / crop loans,
- Working capital credit for activities allied to agriculture and
- Term credit (repayable beyond 12 months)

However, it is to be ensured that transaction records of different loan facilities are kept distinct.

Objectives of Issuing Kisan Credit Card

The objectives underlying the issue of kisan credit card are:

- 1) As a pioneering credit delivery innovation, Kisan Credit Card Scheme aims at provision of adequate and timely support from the banking system to the farmers for their cultivation needs including purchase of inputs in a flexible and cost effective manner;
- 2) To provide adequate and timely credit for the comprehensive credit requirements of farmers for taking up agriculture and allied activities under single window;
- 3) To provide credit in a flexible and simplified procedure;
- 4) To adopt whole farm approach, including the short-term credit needs and a reasonable component for consumption needs, including repayment of farmer's dues to non-institutional lenders;
- 5) To meet the short term production need/working capital needs in respect of the allied activities like poultry, dairy,

- pisciculture, floriculture, horticulture etc.;
- 6) To bring about flexibility and operational freedom in credit utilization;

Eligibility of Farmers

The eligibility of farmers for availing kisan credit card facility is mentioned herein below:

- Farmers those who are owner cultivators/share-croppers/bargadars
- Pattaholders (i.e. land allotees) and Tenants Farmers forming “Joint Liability Group”
- KCC is issued to individual borrower only on merit and not to corporate body society, association, club, group etc.
- Contract farmers under tie-ups with sugarcane, potato, vegetables, fruits and horticultural crops processing units and other processing units in allied agricultural activities.

Contents of Kisan Credit Card

- Beneficiaries covered under the Scheme are issued with a credit card and a pass book or a credit card cum pass book incorporating the name, address, particulars of land holding, borrowing limit, validity period, a passport size photograph of holder etc., which may serve both as an identity card and facilitate recording of transactions on an ongoing basis.
- Borrower is required to produce the card cum pass book whenever he/she operates the account.

Salient Features of The Kisan Credit Card Scheme

The salient features of kisan credit card scheme are:

- Eligible farmers to be provided with a Kisan Credit Card and a pass book or card-cum-pass book.
- Revolving cash credit facility involving any number of withdrawals and repayments within the limit.
- Limit to be fixed on the basis of operational land holding, cropping pattern and scale of finance.
- Entire production credit needs for full year plus ancillary activities related to crop production to be considered while fixing limit.
- Sub-limits may be fixed at the discretion of banks.
- Card is valid for 3 years subject to annual review. As incentive for good performance, credit limits could be enhanced to take care of increase in costs, change in cropping pattern, etc.
- Each withdrawal is to be repaid within a maximum period of 12 months.
- Conversion/reschedulement of loans is also permissible in case of damage to crops due to natural calamities.
- Security, margin, rate of interest, etc. as per RBI norms.
- Operations may be through issuing branch (and also PACS in the case of Cooperative Banks) through other designated branches at the discretion of bank.

- Withdrawals through slips/cheques accompanied by card and passbook.

Problems in Kisan Credit Card

The problems confronted with kisan credit card are mentioned herein below:

- The co-operative banks, which have issued kisan credit cards, are facing financial problems and sponsor banks of the co-operative banks and the state governments have taken no effective step to improve their financial health.
- The farmers have very small agriculture land holdings -- the basis on which they get loans. Due to small landholdings, they get less loan amount.
- One of the main reasons behind farmers showing little interest in KCC is that the latter's rate of interest is almost same as that of other loans.
- Banks delay loans as farmers fall in the high-risk group.

- Flexibility of withdrawals from a branch other than the issuing branch at the discretion of the bank
- Simplifies disbursement procedures
- Removes rigidity regarding cash and kind
- No need to apply for a loan for every crop
- Assured availability of credit at any time enabling reduced interest burden for the farmer.
- Helps buy seeds, fertilizers at farmer's convenience and choice
- Helps buy on cash-avail discount from dealers
- Maximum credit limit based on agriculture income
- Repayment only after harvest
- Rate of interest as applicable to agriculture advance

Advantages of The Kisan Credit Card Scheme

The advantages of issuing kisan credit card are depicted herein below:

- Access to adequate and timely credit to farmers
- Full year's credit requirement of the borrower taken care of.
- Minimum paper work and simplification of documentation for withdrawal of funds from the bank.
- Flexibility to draw cash and buy inputs.
- Assured availability of credit at any time enabling reduced interest burden for the farmer.

Kisan Credit Card Scheme - State-wise Progress

(As at end-March 2009)

(Amount in Rs. crore and Number of cards issued in '000)

Sr. No.	State	Co-operative Banks			Regional Rural Banks			Commercial Banks		Total*	
		No. **	Cards Issued	Amount Sanctioned	No. **	Cards Issued	Amount Sanctioned	Cards Issued	Amount Sanctioned	Cards Issued	Amount Sanctioned
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1.	Andhra Pradesh	22	3,594	6,751.0	5	1,853	3,739.2	8,985	27,986.6	14,432	38,476.8
2.	Assam	1	13	14.9	2	123	411.1	327	582.0	463	1,008.0
3.	Arunachal Pradesh	1	1	1.5	1	3	3.4	16	29.1	19	34.0
4.	Bihar	22	796	944.8	4	839	2,936.0	1,493	6,178.0	3,128	10,058.8
5.	Gujarat	18	1,182	18,377.6	3	242	2,590.2	1,377	20,712.0	2,801	41,679.8
6.	Goa \$	1	4	17.8	-	-	-	11	130.4	15	148.2
7.	Haryana	19	1,244	7,732.1	2	336	2,907.5	768	7,719.2	2,348	18,358.8
8.	Himachal Pradesh	3	66	318.1	2	40	179.0	219	1,141.7	325	1,638.7
9.	Jammu & Kashmir	4	52	72.5	3	15	122.4	12	76.8	78	271.7
10.	Karnataka	21	1,677	6,872.9	6	1,097	5,376.6	2,266	13,011.3	5,041	25,260.8
11.	Kerala	14	1,295	3,470.7	2	424	1,475.1	1,405	4,885.5	3,124	9,831.3
12.	Madhya Pradesh	38	3,118	13,352.2	8	474	2,415.5	1,559	12,002.2	5,151	27,769.9
13.	Maharashtra	30	5,217	30,802.9	4	276	1,100.0	2,426	10,949.4	7,919	42,852.3
14.	Meghalaya	1	10	13.2	1	21	36.6	37	95.1	68	144.9
15.	Mizoram	1	2	1.3	1	9	43.9	12	23.7	23	68.9
16.	Manipur	1	13	33.6	1	2	2.7	25	61.3	40	97.6
17.	Nagaland	1	2	0.8	1	1	2.9	18	33.4	22	37.1
18.	Orissa	17	3,268	9,587.0	5	597	1,299.5	1,069	3,124.6	4,934	14,011.2
19.	Punjab	19	892	6,199.5	3	119	1,293.9	1,219	13,511.1	2,230	21,004.4
20.	Rajasthan	28	2,851	8,387.0	6	440	3,595.6	1,467	16,573.5	4,757	28,556.1
21.	Sikkim \$	1	3	6.3	-	-	-	7	22.8	9	29.1
22.	Tamil Nadu	22	1,803	5,228.9	2	265	588.9	3,741	11,776.4	5,809	17,594.2
23.	Tripura	1	4	5.6	1	41	62.5	52	106.2	97	174.3
24.	Uttar Pradesh	51	6,074	5,910.0	12	3,343	11,167.9	6,005	33,075.3	15,423	50,153.3
25.	West Bengal	20	1,463	5,494.9	3	311	1,357.5	1,334	3,964.4	3,108	10,816.7
26.	Andaman and Nicobar Islands \$	1	3	8.3	-	-	-	2	8.0	6	16.3
27.	Chandigarh \$	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	15.3	3	15.3
28.	Daman & Diu @	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	13.9	2	13.9
29.	New Delhi \$	1	2	8.8	-	-	-	20	173.0	22	181.8
30.	D & N Haveli @\$	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	28.4	3	28.4
31.	Lakshadweep @\$	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	2.6	1	2.6
32.	Puducherry	1	7	34.3	1	-	-	48	172.2	56	206.5
33.	Jharkhand	8	279	544.3	2	300	340.5	414	1,067.8	992	1,952.7
34.	Chhattisgarh	7	912	2,195.0	3	256	613.4	262	1,296.6	1,430	4,105.0
35.	Uttarakhand	10	298	600.7	2	45	170.4	260	2,433.6	603	3,204.8
36.	Other States	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.05	0.1	0.05	0.1
	Total	385	36,145	1,32,988.2	86	11,471	43,832.3	37,051	1,93,249.5	84,667	3,70,070.08

Source: NABARD

AGENCY WISE KCCs ISSUED

(Rs In Lakhs)

Year	Cooperative banks	RRBs	Public Sector Commercial Banks	Total
1998-1999	1.56	0.06	6.22	7.64
1999-2000	35.95	1.73	13.66	51.34
2000-2001	56.14	6.48	23.90	86.52
2001-2002	54.36	8.34	30.71	93.41
2002-2003	45.79	9.64	27	82.43
2003-2004	48.78	12.75	30.94	92.47
2004-2005	35.56	17.29	43.95	96.80
2005-2006	25.98	12.49	41.65	80.12
2006-2007	22.97	14.05	48.08	65.11
2007-2008	20.91	17.73	46.06	84.70
2008-2009 (upto Feb'09)	10.63	12.05	24.57	47.26
Total	358.63	112.63	336.74	808.00

Source: NABARD

During 2007-08, 84.7 lakh KCCs amounting with limits aggregating Rs. 88,264 crore were issued. During 2008-09 (till February 2009), a total of 47.26 lakh KCCs amounting with limits aggregating Rs. 26,828 crore were issued.

Various Attempts By Banks Towards Agriculture Finance

The various attempts made by banks on the front of agriculture finance includes the following:

- 1) **Allahabad Bank:** It offers the Kisan Credit Card and Kisan Shakti Yojana Scheme. The Kisan Credit Card is a unique scheme for farmers through which they can draw a cash loan for crop production as well as for domestic needs from the card-issuing branch within the sanctioned limit. The Kisan Shakti Yojana provides farm investment credit, as well as

personal/domestic loans including repayment of debt to moneylenders. The permissible loan limit is 50 per cent of the value of land or 5 times the net farm income, whichever is lower, less the outstanding amount, if any, in April.

- 2) **Andhra Bank:** It provides facilities to farmers like AB Kisan Vikas Card, AB Pattabhi Agricard, AB Kisan Chakra, rural godowns, agri clinics, agri service centres, self help groups and solar cookers. They also provide other schemes such as Kisan Sampathi, tractor financing, Kisan Green Card, Surya Sakhti and loans to dairy agents.
- 3) **Bank of Baroda:** It offers farmers the Baroda Kisan Credit Card. It also has schemes for the purchase of agricultural

- implements, heavy agricultural machinery like tractors, irrigation and other infrastructure. Bank of Baroda also finances the development of agri industries like horticulture, sericulture, fisheries, dairy and poultry.
- 4) **Bank of India:** It has a Kisan Credit Card Scheme that helps farmers raise short-term funds for agriculture and other farm-based activities, on an on-going basis, with very flexible and friendly repayment terms. It also offers an agricultural loan for development of agriculture related industries, purchase of machinery and other agricultural purposes.
 - 5) **Bank of Maharashtra:** It offers agriculturists a Mahabank Kisan Credit Card and financial schemes for digging new wells, purchasing harvesters, livestock, vehicles and land. Repayment terms for different agricultural loans range from three to fifteen years.
 - 6) **Canara Bank:** It provides Kisan Credit Cards. Limits up to 50,000 have no margin while those above 50,000 have a margin of 15 to 20 percent. Other than this, Canara Bank provides a wide array of financial schemes for different agricultural purposes.
 - 7) **Central Bank of India:** The Central Kisan Credit Card is a credit service provided to farmers on the basis of their holdings for purchasing agricultural inputs. Only those farmers having a good track record for the past 2 years with the bank as a borrower or depositor and who are not defaulters to any credit institution would be considered for loans.
 - 8) **Corporation Bank:** It offers a range of loan schemes to farmers. They are the Corp Gram Mitra Yojana, Corp Arthias Loan Yojana, Corp Kisan Tie-Up Loan Scheme, Corp Kisan Farm Mechanisation Scheme and Corp Kisan Vehicle Loan Yojna.
 - 9) **Dena Bank:** Dena Bank has sponsored 2 Regional Rural Banks namely Dena Gujarat Gramin Bank in Gujarat and Durg Rajnandgaon Gramin Bank (DRGB) in Chhattisgarh. The bank has set up a Rural Development Foundation for training unemployed youth in rural areas. Other financial schemes of the bank are the Dena Swacch Gram Yojana, Dena Kisan Gold Credit Card Scheme and the Dena Bhumiheen Kisan Credit Card Scheme.
 - 10) **Indian Bank:** It has a wide range of schemes for agriculturalists such as Swarojgar Credit Card, Gramin Mahila Sowbhagya Scheme, Kisan Bike Loan Scheme, Yuva Kisan Vidya Nidhi Yojana and Indian Bank Kisan Card Scheme.
 - 11) **Indian Overseas Bank:** It offers agri-business consultancy services that include conducting feasibility and market studies, preparation of detailed project reports and formulation of

- rehabilitation packages for sick agro units.
- 12) **Oriental Bank of Commerce:** It has two agricultural projects - the Grameen Project and the Comprehensive Village Development Programme. The Grameen Project involves disbursing small loans ranging from Rs. 75 onwards to mostly women. Training is also provided in villages in using locally available raw material to produce pickles and jams. The Comprehensive Village Development Programme focuses on providing an integrated package of rural finance to villagers to build up their village.
 - 13) **Punjab and Sind Bank:** It offers a range of financial schemes for farmers like the Zimidara Credit Card, tractor finance scheme, drip irrigation scheme, Kheti Udyog Khazana Yojana, vermi composting scheme, horticulture clinic and private veterinary clinic with dairy unit scheme.
 - 14) **Punjab National Bank:** This bank has a special website called PNB Krishi for agriculturalists. It gives details on crop practices, plant protection, farm machinery, market prices and other farming news and activities. The website also provides a list of financial schemes offered by Punjab National Bank on production credit, investment credit, composite loans, animal husbandry and farm mechanization.
 - 15) **Syndicate Bank:** It offers a wide range of agricultural loan products such as the Synd Jai Kisan Loan Scheme, Jewel Loan Scheme for Agriculture, Syndicate Farm House Scheme, Finance for Hi-tech Agriculture, Development of Irrigation Infrastructure scheme, Syndicate 2/3/4 Wheelers Scheme and the Syndicate Kisan Credit Card (SKCC).
 - 16) **UCO Bank:** This Bank provides the UCO Hira Jayanti Krishi Yojana to meet the long-term credit needs of the farming community in rural areas for agriculture, allied activities as well as for personal purposes. Only farmers below 60 years are eligible to apply. Minimum quantum of the loan is Rs. 25,000/- and the maximum is Rs. 5 lakhs.
 - 17) **Union Bank of India:** UBI provides facilities to farmers include Kisan ATM Cards and special Kisan ATM Machines. These ATM's are easy to operate and do not require farmers to have a high level of literacy. They are voice enabled in the local language, have a touch screen monitor and work on a bio-metric authentication system like finger print verification.
 - 18) **United Bank of India:** The range of financial schemes offered to agriculturalists include the United Krishi Laghu

Paribahan Yojana, United Krishi Sahayak Yojana, United Gramyashree Yojana, Gramin Bhandaran Yojana and the United Bhumiheen Kisan Credit Card.

This scheme provides a simple package to farmers to meet entire agricultural credit requirements such as crop production, investment credit and consumption credit. All farmers including owners, tenant cultivators, leased land farmers and sharecroppers are eligible for this scheme.

19) **Vijaya Bank:** This bank offers one comprehensive financial scheme known as the Vijaya Krishi Vikas (VKV) Scheme.

A Survey Conducted In Village Asmoli With Respect To Kisan Credit Card Issued By Prathma Bank

PRATHMA KISAN CREDIT CARD	
Purpose	The scheme aims at meeting short term requirements of a farmer. The farmer is free to make frequent debit and credit transaction in the account.
Eligibility	All the farmers residing in the operational area of the branch.
Quantum	The limit of the card is fixed as per the cropping pattern adopted or to be adopted by the farmer. The cost of cultivation is determined as per the scale of finance fixed by the District Technical Committee
Margin	No margin up to limit of 50,000. While 15 % Above 50,000
Repayment	The validity of the card is for 3 years which is subjected renewal after annual review. The amount is to be repaid as per cash flow of the farmer i.e. crop harvesting depending upon the duration of the crops. However, generally, every debits are to be credited within one year.
Security	Simple Registered Mortgage or charge creation over agriculture land & Third party of 2 co-obligants

A small survey was conducted in village Asmoli in Tehseel Sambhal District Moradabad to find out the pattern of agriculture finance with reference to Kisan Credit Card. A sample size of 50 farmers was chosen. A questionnaire was prepared.

The analysis of the survey is as follows:

(1) The Age of farmers covered in sample.

- | | |
|--------------------|------------|
| (a) Below 40 years | 14 farmers |
| (b) Above 40 years | 36 farmers |

28 percent farmers in survey are below 40 years of age and 72 percent farmers are above 40 years as the agricultural land is in the name of fathers and not the sons.

(2) Size of farm holdings held by farmers

- | | |
|---------------------|------------|
| (a) 0 - 10 bighas | 10 farmers |
| (b) 11 – 50 bighas | 28 farmers |
| (c) Above 50 bighas | 12 farmers |

24 percent of the farmers have agriculture land above 50 bighas, 20 percent farmers have land less than 10 bighas and 56 percent farmers have agriculture land between 10 to 50 bighas.

(3) Amount of loan availed by farmers covered in survey (In Rs)

- | | |
|-------------------|------------|
| (a) 0 – 10000 | 12 farmers |
| (b) 10000 – 50000 | 32 farmers |
| (c) Above 50000 | 06 farmers |

24 percent of the farmers in sample have taken loans with in a limit of Rs. 10000. 64 percent of the farmers have taken loans with in the range of Rs. 10000 to Rs. 50000. However, only 12 percent farmers have taken loans above the amount of Rs. 500000, particularly for purchasing necessary agricultural equipments.

(4) Utilisation of loan amount for different purposes.

- | | |
|--|------------|
| (a) Purchase of seeds, fertilizers and other irrigation facilities | 32 farmers |
| (b) Purchase of equipments | 14 farmers |
| (c) Personal consumption | 04 farmers |

64 percent of the farmers have utilized the loan amount for purchasing seeds, fertilizers, insecticides and for irrigation facilities. 28 percent of the farmers have utilized the loan amount for the purchase of agricultural equipments and machinery. However, few farmers around 8 percent used some part of the loan amount for personal consumption.

(5) Adequacy of Loan Amount.

- | | |
|-------------------------------|------------|
| (a) Amount of Loan adequate | 35 farmers |
| (b) Amount of Loan inadequate | 15 farmers |

70 percent of the farmers were of the view that the amount of credit is sufficient to their requirements. However, 30 percent were of the view that amount of loan sanctioned to them is insufficient to meet their requirements.

(6) Farmers availing Cheque Facility

- (a) Availed 12 farmers
- (b) Not availed 38 farmers

Farmers around 76 percent did not avail the facility of cheque book, as they withdraw the amount through withdrawal slip. Also suppliers of inputs generally prefer to accept cash payments. Only 24 percent has availed the facility of cheque book.

(7) Whether farmers are satisfied with the facilities given by bank with regard to KCC?

- (a) Satisfied 45 farmers
- (b) Not Satisfied 05 farmers

90 percent farmers covered in sample are satisfied with the facilities provided by bank. Only a meager 10 percent of the farmers were unsatisfied, may be due to some bad experiences with the bank officials or not getting adequate credit.

Other Findings of The Survey

Apart from the above findings, some other important findings of the survey are:

- 1) **Repayment dates:** It was satisfying to know that almost all the farmers covered in the sample were aware of the repayment dates. The role of banks in educating the farmer in use of Kisan Credit Card had been quite effective. Banks were giving special treatment to perennial crops wherever necessary. Branch Managers were effectively exercising their discretion to fix the due dates for repayment according to the harvesting/ marketing season.
- 2) **Purchase of fertilizer and other inputs:** The KCC has proved to be very useful to the farmers for purchase of inputs in a cost effective manner.
- 3) **End use of credit:** Though there were no systematic monitoring of

the end use of the credit, the credit under KCC were mostly used for agricultural operation purposes. A portion of the limit were also being utilised for consumption purposes. Branch managers felt that the amount under KCC was not misutilised

- 4) **Operations on the KCC:** Most of the farmers did not operate the KCC as envisaged under the scheme due to the following:
 - Farmers' apprehension that once they repay the loan they may not get a repeat loan.
 - Complicated procedure of withdrawal based on seasonal sub-limits under the total limit.
- 5) **Facility of withdrawals from other branches:** Almost all cooperative banks and most of the RRBs had not extended this facility to their card holders owing to operational considerations. However, where banks are offering this facility under Kisan Credit Card, there is reportedly low demand for this facility by farmers due to upfront commission at the rate of 2 to 3 per cent of the amount of cash drawn, charged by the banks.

- 6) **Coverage of new farmers:** New farmers are being issued KCCs by the banks as they are getting attracted due to many factors such as effective publicity by the banks, utility of Kisan Credit Card and the continuous monitoring of the progress by RBI and NABARD.
- 7) **Repayment instructions:** Although the limit sanctioned under the Kisan Credit Card is in the nature of revolving cash credit and each withdrawal is repayable within 12 months, yet all the banks had fixed specific repayment norms while sanctioning credit limit under Kisan Credit Card.

Suggestions

After going through the present study the researchers present the following suggestions to improve the efficiency in the structure of agriculture finance:

- 1) There is a need to upscale the outreach of KCC to cover all the eligible farmers by creating greater awareness and giving greater publicity to the scheme.
- 2) Updation of land records and sensitisation of bank staff through training programmes will further add to the spread of the scheme.
- 3) The exercise of preparing special agricultural credit plans with higher component of direct finance with a special thrust on small and marginal farmers should also receive high priority.
- 4) People are depending on agriculture because they do not have other skills and therefore, have to be there because they

cannot go anywhere. There is need to bring in large scale investments in agriculture through PPP and even FDI should be welcomed.

- 5) There should be a provision of financing the entire supply chain. This calls for financing not only for raising crops, tractor financing and some dairy, poultry, sheep and goats, but also entire gamut of rural financing viz; fruits and vegetables, horticulture crops and activities related to post harvest operations i.e. sorting, grading, processing, packaging, storing, transporting and marketing. This would call for investments in sunrise industries such as Agro Processing, Agri-Marketing, Bio-technology, Post harvest Management, Organic Farming, Cold chain financing, cold storage, Rural Godowns, Financing against warehouse receipt.
- 6) Government involvement required, particularly to address the poor farmers.
- 7) Agricultural economists can support generation of new ideas on financial services

Conclusion

The study notes that both formal and informal sources of credit are important in the India context. However, the significance of formal credit institutions in terms of credit delivery for the agricultural sector has increased over time. Agricultural credit has played a vital role in supporting agricultural production in India. The analysis reveals that the credit delivery to the agriculture

sector continues to be insufficient. It appears that the banking system is still hesitant on various grounds to provide credit to small and marginal farmers. The Green Revolution characterised by a greater use of inputs like fertilizers, seeds and other inputs, increased credit requirements which were provided by the agricultural financial institutions. Though the outreach and the amount of agricultural credit have increased over the years, several weaknesses have crept in which have affected the viability and sustainability of these institutions. Furthermore, outdated legal framework and the outdated tenancy laws have hampered flow of credit and development of strong and efficient agricultural credit institutions. A review of performance of agricultural credit in India reveals that though the overall flow of institutional credit has increased over the years, there are several gaps in the system like inadequate provision of credit to small and marginal farmers, paucity of medium and long-term lending and limited deposit mobilisation and heavy dependence on borrowed funds by major agricultural credit purveyors. These have major implications for agricultural development as also the well being of the farming community. Efforts are therefore required to address and rectify these issues.

To conclude, an assessment of agriculture credit situation brings out the fact that the credit delivery to the agriculture sector continues to be inadequate. It appears that the banking system is still hesitant on various grounds to purvey credit to small and marginal farmers. The situation calls for concerted efforts to augment the flow of credit to agriculture, alongside exploring

new innovations in product design and methods of delivery, through better use of technology and related processes.

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